

Dual action of benzaldehydes: Inhibiting quorum sensing and enhancing antibiotic efficacy for controlling *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilms

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ABSTRACT

Quorum sensing (QS) has a central role in biofilm lifestyle and antimicrobial resistance, and disrupting these signaling pathways is a promising strategy to control bacterial pathogenicity and virulence. In this study, the efficacy of three structurally related benzaldehydes (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (vanillin) and 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (syringaldehyde)) in disrupting the *las* and *pqs* systems of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was investigated using bioreporter strains and computational simulations. Additionally, these benzaldehydes were combined with tobramycin and ciprofloxacin antibiotics to evaluate their ability to increase antibiotic efficacy in preventing and eradicating *P. aeruginosa* biofilms. To this end, the total biomass, metabolic activity and culturability of the biofilm cells were determined. *In vitro* assays results indicated that the aromatic aldehydes have potential to inhibit the *las* and *pqs* systems by > 80 %. Molecular docking studies supported these findings, revealing the aldehydes binding in the same pocket as the natural ligands or receptor proteins (LasR, PQSA, PQSE, PQSR). Benzaldehydes were shown to act as virulence factor attenuators, with vanillin achieving a 48 % reduction in pyocyanin production. The benzaldehyde-tobramycin combination led not only to a 60 % reduction in biomass production but also to a 90 % reduction in the metabolic activity of established biofilms. A similar result was observed when benzaldehydes were combined with ciprofloxacin. 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde demonstrated relevant action in increasing biofilm susceptibility to ciprofloxacin, resulting in a 65 % reduction in biomass. This study discloses, for the first time, that the benzaldehydes studied are potent QS inhibitors and also enhancers of antibiotics antibiofilm activity against *P. aeruginosa*.

1. Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic pathogen known to cause serious and persistent infections, especially in immunocompromised individuals [1]. The treatment of these infections, especially those associated with biofilms, is a major challenge. In the sessile state, the bacterial cells have a higher degree of protection, which makes them highly resistant to host defences and to various antibiotics [2]. In addition, *P. aeruginosa* can modulate its pathogenicity and virulence

facilitating the establishment of the infection in the host. This ability is primarily mediated by cell-cell communication in bacteria, known as quorum sensing (QS) [2].

The QS is an important mechanism used by numerous bacteria to modulate gene expression and to respond to stress signals from the environment [3]. This intercellular communication is mediated by extracellular signalling molecules called autoinducers (AIs). These molecules are released by the bacteria into the surrounding medium and their concentration depends on the density of the bacterial population [4]. When their concentration reaches a certain threshold (quorum

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Abbreviation list

AI	Autoinducer	LBA	Luria-Bertani agar
AB	Alamar blue	LCPS	Light counts per second
ANOVA	Analysis of variance	MAR	Metabolic activity reduction
BMAR	Biofilm cells metabolic activity reduction	MBC	Minimum bactericidal concentration
BR	Biomass removal	MHB	Mueller-Hinton broth
BPR	Biomass production reduction	MHA	Mueller-Hinton agar
BSD	Biofilms Structural Database	MIC	Minimum inhibitory concentration
CLSI	Clinical and laboratory standards institute	ns	Non-significant
CV	Crystal violet	ne	No effect
CZG	2-[(5-nitro-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)sulfanyl]-N-(4-phenoxyphenyl)	OD	Optical density
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide	OHN	n-3-oxo-dodecanoyl-l-homoserine lactone
FC30	(Z)-4-bromo-5-(bromomethylene)-2(5H)-furanone	PCA	Plate count agar
HHQ	4-hydroxy-2-heptylquinoline	PDB	Protein Databank
KYX	N-{4-[(2,2-dimethylpropyl)carbamamido]phenyl}-1H-indazole-7-carboxamide	PQS	3,4-dihydroxy-2-heptylquinoline or pseudomonas quinolone signal
LBB	Luria-Bertani broth	QS	Quorum sensing
		QSI	Quorum sensing inhibitors
		3UK	5'-O-[(S)-[(2-aminobenzoyl)oxy](hydroxy)phosphoryl]adenosine

level), the AIs can bind to the corresponding receptors. This binding triggers a cascade of intracellular events that lead to the activation of certain genes, which influences antibiotic resistance, biofilm formation and maturation, swarming motility, virulence, and modulation of the host immune response [5,6]. In particular, *P. aeruginosa* has four different QS systems (*las*, *rhl*, *pqs* and *iqs*), which are arranged hierarchically [3]. Through these QS systems, this bacterium influences the synthesis of various virulence factors, including proteases, exotoxin A, siderophores (pyoverdine and pyochelin) and pyocyanin [7]. These virulence factors allow *P. aeruginosa* to coordinate and change their behaviour, and respond collectively to the surrounding environment [8]. In addition, AIs produced by *P. aeruginosa* may also play an important role in modelling infection in the host. These signalling molecules show the ability to induce significant cell death in host lymphocytes, which promotes bacterial survival [9]. Furthermore, the mutual action of AIs with virulence factors (e.g. pyocyanin), facilitates an increase in the number of persistent cells [10]. This kind of cells can be related to the persistence of chronic infections and a possible explanation for the recalcitrance of biofilm infections. It is, therefore, clear that QS not only plays an important role in biofilm formation but also modulates the response of the host immune system.

By interrupting bacterial communication, it may be possible to reduce the virulence of *P. aeruginosa* and increase the effectiveness of conventional antibiotics [1]. The use of QS inhibitors (QSI) could open up a new avenue in the fight against antibiotic-resistant infections, especially when bacterial biofilms are formed. The use of QSI can improve the activity of antibiotics, allowing lower doses to be used and avoiding the widespread prescription of broad-spectrum antibiotics [11]. Despite the current limitations of QSI (e.g. furanones) in clinical use due to their low bioavailability and high toxicity, ongoing research aims to find alternative strategies [4,12].

The exploitation of naturally occurring QSI, especially those derived from plants, represents an environmentally sustainable strategy, making it even more appealing [13]. Moreover, natural compounds have been employed by humans since ancient times [14]. Benzaldehydes are a group of plant secondary metabolites, i.e. phytochemicals, and are important intermediates for the production of various chemical products of industrial value (i.e. pharmaceuticals, food aromas, dyes and fragrances) [15]. Among the aldehydes studied so far for their antimicrobial properties, vanillin stands out for its significant ability to interfere with the QS pathways, including with the *pqs* and *cvi* QS systems from *P. aeruginosa* and *Chromobacterium violaceum*, respectively [12,16].

Building upon on the promising results described for vanillin, this study explored, for the first time, two natural and structural analogues of this benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and syringaldehyde, as potential inhibitors of the *P. aeruginosa las* and *pqs* systems. Although vanillin has been previously studied for its inhibitory effects on the *pqs* expression, its impact on the *las* system has never been studied. Therefore, it was used as a reference, only for the *pqs* assays. Molecular docking simulations were performed to corroborate the *in vitro* data. In addition, the effect of selected aromatic aldehydes in attenuating the production of virulence factors (pyocyanin and pyoverdine inhibition) was also investigated. On the other hand, the ability of the selected benzaldehydes to increase the efficacy of antibiotics tobramycin and ciprofloxacin in preventing and eradicating biofilms was also investigated. Finally, additional tests were conducted to evaluate the increased susceptibility of 24-h-old biofilms formed in the presence of the benzaldehydes to tobramycin and ciprofloxacin.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Bacteria and growth conditions

The bacterial strains used in this study are listed in Table 1. The *P. aeruginosa* PA14 wild type and the reporter strain *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 constructed by Massai et al. [17], were used for screening the QS inhibitory activity in the *las* system [4]. *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 wild-type and *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 pqsA CTXluxHpqsA biosensor (PAO1-CTX) were used to evaluate the inhibitory activity in the *pqs* system [18]. These strains were kindly provided by Professor Paul Williams from the Centre for Biomolecular Sciences, University of Nottingham (Nottingham, UK). *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145 was obtained from American Type Culture Collection. This strain was used as a model microorganism for antibacterial tests with phytochemicals and antibiotics and for biofilm control assays [19]. The strains were preserved at -80 °C in cryovials containing 30 % (v/v) glycerol (VWR, Belgium) and with specific culture broths: Mueller-Hinton broth (MHB, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145, Luria-Bertani broth (LBB; Liofilchem, Roseto degli Abruzzi, Italy) for *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT, *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 and *P. aeruginosa* PAO1-WT and LBB with 20 µg mL⁻¹ of gentamicin for *P. aeruginosa* PAO1-CTX. When necessary, subcultures were established on the specific corresponding solid medium (Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA), Luria-Bertani agar (LBA) and LBA with 20 µg mL⁻¹ of gentamicin) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h (precultures).

Table 1Description of the *P. aeruginosa* strains used in this study and the respective assays.

<i>P. aeruginosa</i> strains	Description	Assays used	Reference
PA14-WT	Wild type	QS inhibition assays - <i>las</i> system; pyocyanin and pyoverdine production	[17]
PA14-R3	<i>LasI</i> mutant containing the PrsaL:luxCDABE transcriptional fusion integrated into the chromosome at the attB neutral site	QS inhibition assays - <i>las</i> system	[17]
PAO1-WT	Wild type	QS inhibition assays - <i>pqs</i> system; pyocyanin production	[18]
PAO1-CTX	<i>PqsA</i> mutant containing a copy of the <i>PqsA</i> promoter linked to the luxCDABE genes and inserted into a neutral site in the chromosome	QS inhibition assays - <i>pqs</i> system	[18]
ATCC 10145	Whole-genome sequenced strain	Antibacterial susceptibility assays; Biofilm control assays	[21]

Working cultures were then prepared by subculturing cells from the precultures in the respective medium at 37 °C in a shaking incubator (150 rpm, AGITORB 200, Aralab, Rio de Mouro, Portugal).

2.2. Phytochemicals and antibiotics

4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde were purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co, Ltd (TCI-Tokyo, Japan). All benzaldehydes are >95 % pure by high performance liquid chromatography or gas chromatography analysis. Stock solutions of the benzaldehydes were prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, Avantor, VWR, Radnor, PA, USA) immediately before use. The DMSO percentage used was 50 % (v/v) for biofilm eradication studies and 10 % (v/v) for all the other assays. In cases where the MIC was not detected, 1000 µg mL⁻¹ of benzaldehydes was considered the maximum concentration tested (MTC). The antibiotics ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (quinolone class) and tobramycin (aminoglycoside class) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA) and TCI, respectively with purity >95 %. Antibiotic stock solutions were prepared in sterile distilled water according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines and stored at -20 °C until use [20].

2.3. Evaluation of the antibacterial activity

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of benzaldehydes and antibiotics was determined using the broth microdilution method following CLSI guidelines [22,23]. Briefly, after overnight bacterial growth (37 °C in MHB/LBB), the optical density (OD, λ = 600 nm) was adjusted spectrophotometrically using fresh MHB/LBB to 0.132 ± 0.02 (10⁶ CFU mL⁻¹ for all other strains). Sterile 96-well polystyrene (PS) microtiter plates (Orange Scientific, Braine-l'Alleud, Belgium) were then filled with 180 µL of cells and 20 µL of selected phytochemicals/antibiotics (10 % v/v of the well) at different concentrations (phytochemicals - 6.25 to 1000 µg mL⁻¹; antibiotics - 0.0625 to 1024 µg mL⁻¹) for each strain of *P. aeruginosa*. The microtiter plates were then incubated for 24 h at 37 °C on an orbital shaker (150 rpm). Cell suspensions with DMSO and cell suspensions without benzaldehydes/antibiotics were used as negative controls. The absorbance (λ = 600 nm) was measured before (t = 0 h) and after (t = 24 h) incubation period using a microplate

reader (Synergy HT, Biotek, Winooski, VT, USA). The MIC was recorded as the lowest concentration that inhibits bacterial growth (where the final OD is equal to or less than the initial OD). The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of benzaldehydes/antibiotics represents the lowest concentration tested at which complete inhibition of bacterial growth is observed [24]. For this purpose, 10 µL of the contents of the wells corresponding to concentrations of the benzaldehydes/antibiotics equal to or higher than the MIC were taken and plated on plate count agar (PCA or LB agar-LBA) plates and then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. MIC and MBC values were used as the reference for the rest of the experiments.

2.4. Evaluation of the QS inhibition activity: in vitro studies

The *in vitro* anti-QS activity of the aromatic aldehydes was studied for the *las* and *pqs* systems of *P. aeruginosa*. In this way, a target-oriented screening with genetically modified strains (insertion of QS reporter plasmids) was carried out. Thus, the binding of the autoinducer to the receptor of the genetically modified strains leads to the expression of the *luxCDABE* operon and the production of light-generating proteins. The enzyme luciferase, which is produced by the *luxAB* proteins, oxidises the reduced flavin mononucleotide and a long-chain fatty aldehyde, thereby generating light. This light is only emitted when exposed to autoinducers, as the genetically modified bacteria used in these assays do not produce natural autoinducers [18].

Negative and positive controls were used to ensure the validity of the results and to compare the effects of the tested compounds. In this sense, a cell suspension with DMSO and a cell suspension without the benzaldehydes were used as negative controls for these assays. A specific positive control was used for each system. For the assays related to the *las* system, a cell suspension with (Z)-4-bromo-5-(bromomethylene)-2(5H)-furanone (FC30 at 2.5 µg mL⁻¹) was used [7]. In addition, furvina (at 12.5 µg mL⁻¹) was also used as a positive control because it is a potent inhibitor that was previously studied by our research group [4]. On the other hand, the evaluation of vanillin at different concentrations (100, 400 and 1000 µg mL⁻¹) was used as a positive control for the *pqs* system. This benzaldehyde was previously identified as an inhibitor of the *pqs* system [16].

2.4.1. Detection of the QS inhibition activity in the *las* system

The ability of the aromatic aldehydes to affect the *las* system of *P. aeruginosa* was performed using a co-culture assay (*P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 and *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT) [17]. Briefly, after overnight bacterial growth in LBA, some colonies were scraped from the agar plate surfaces and diluted in LBB. Then, the OD (λ = 600 nm) of *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 and *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT was adjusted to 0.045 (10⁷ CFU mL⁻¹) and 0.015 (10⁷ CFU mL⁻¹), respectively (reporter/wild-type ratio of 3:1). Subsequently, black (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and transparent 96-well microtiter plates of polystyrene (PS), with opaque or clear flat bottom, respectively, were filled with 180 µL of the co-culture and 20 µL of the benzaldehydes (6.25–1000 µg mL⁻¹). The microplates were then incubated for 4 h at 37 °C in a shaking incubator (150 rpm). Finally, light counts per second (LCPS) and absorbance (λ = 600 nm) were measured using a microplate reader. Luminescence values were normalised by dividing the LCPS values by the absorbance (λ = 600 nm) values.

2.4.1.1. AIs production and response assays. The influence of benzaldehydes on the production of AI N-(3-oxododecanoyl)-l-homoserine lactone (3-oxo-C12-HSL) was evaluated according to Borges et al. [4]. *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT was cultivated on LBA plates for 24 h at 37 °C. Subsequently, some colonies were collected (by scraping) from the plate surfaces and diluted in LBB. The OD (λ = 600 nm) of the bacterial suspension was adjusted to 0.05 (10⁷ CFU mL⁻¹). Then, 9 mL of the

previously prepared cell suspension was added to 50 mL centrifuge tubes together with 1 mL of the benzaldehydes (at 6.25–1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). The tubes were incubated overnight at 37 °C with shaking (150 rpm). Subsequently, 200 μL of the cell suspension was inoculated into a 96-well clear-bottom PS microtiter plate and absorbance was measured at 600 nm for growth assessment. The remaining cell suspension was centrifuged (3772 \times g) for 15 min and the supernatant was collected and filtered (pore size 0.22 μm , Whatman, Little Chalfont, UK). Then, 20 μL of the supernatant and 180 μL of the PA14-R3 cell suspension (diluted in LBB and with an $\text{OD}_{600\text{ nm}}$ of 0.045) were placed into 96-well black opaque bottom PS microtiter plates and 96-well clear bottom PS microtiter. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 4 h with stirring (150 rpm). Finally, LCPS and absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) were measured using a microplate reader. Luminescence values were normalised by dividing LCPS values by absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) values. A calibration curve was created by growing *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 in the presence of increasing concentrations of synthetic 3-oxo-C12-HSL to calculate the concentration of 3-oxo-C12-HSL in each culture supernatant.

To determine the influence of benzaldehydes on the detection of AI 3-oxo-C12-HSL, a protocol similar to that used for the production of AI was used [7]. *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 was cultivated on LBA plates for 24 h at 37 °C. Then, bacterial cells were scraped from the surface of the agar plate and diluted in LBB. The OD ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) was set to 0.05 (10^7 CFU mL^{-1}). Then, 9 mL of the previously prepared cell suspension was added to 50 mL centrifuge tubes along with 1 mL of the benzaldehydes (at 6.25–1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). The tubes were incubated overnight at 37 °C with shaking (150 rpm). After the incubation period, 200 μL of the cell suspension was placed into a 96-well clear-bottom PS microtiter plate and the absorbance was measured at 600 nm to assess bacterial growth. The OD ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) of the remaining cell suspensions was adjusted to an absorbance value of 0.045. Then, both 96-well black and transparent PS microtiter plates were filled with 180 μL of PA14-R3 cell suspension and 20 μL of synthetic 3-oxo-C12-HSLs (25 μM). The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 4 h and 150 rpm. Finally, LCPS and absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) were measured using a microplate reader. Luminescence values were normalised by dividing the LCPS values by the absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) values.

2.4.2. Detection of the QS inhibition activity in the pqs system

The ability of benzaldehydes to affect the pqs system of *P. aeruginosa* was carried out according to Fletcher et al. [18], with slight modifications. Briefly, after overnight *P. aeruginosa* PAO1-WT growth in LBB, the OD ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) of the bacterial suspension was adjusted to 0.01 (10^6 CFU mL^{-1}). Then, 9 mL of the previously prepared cell suspension was added to 50 mL centrifuge tubes together with 1 mL of the benzaldehydes (at subinhibitory concentrations). The tubes were incubated overnight at 37 °C with shaking (150 rpm). Subsequently, 200 μL of the cell suspension was dispensed into a transparent 96-well PS microtiter plate and the absorbance was measured at 600 nm for growth assessment. The remaining cell suspension was centrifuged (3772 \times g) at 4 °C for 15 min and the supernatant was collected and filtered (pore size 0.22 μm). Then, 100 μL of the supernatant and 100 μL of the *P. aeruginosa*-CTX cell suspension (at an $\text{OD}_{600\text{ nm}}$ of 0.01 (10^6 CFU mL^{-1})) were placed into both black and transparent 96-well PS microtiter plates. The plates were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C with shaking (150

rpm). Finally, LCPS and absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) were measured using a microplate reader. Luminescence values were normalised by dividing LCPS values by the $\text{A}_{600\text{ nm}}$ values.

2.5. Validation of the QS inhibition activity: computational studies

Structural information on the *las* and *pqs* systems of *P. aeruginosa* was obtained from the Protein Databank (PDB) [25] and the Biofilms Structural Database (BSD) [26]. A total of four X-ray structures were used in this study corresponding to the proteins LasR, PqsA, PqsE, and PqsR (details are summarised in Table 2). Only the catalytic domain of each structure was used. The OHN (3-oxo-C12-HSL), 3UK (5'-O-[(2-aminobenzoyl)oxy](hydroxy)phosphoryl]adenosine), KYX (N-{4-[(2,2-dimethylpropyl)carbonylamino]phenyl}-1H-indazole-7-carboxamide), and CZG (2-[(5-nitro-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)sulfonyl]-N-(4-phenoxyphenyl)acetamide) were used as reference ligands for the proteins studied.

Firstly, the PDB structures of the proteins were thoroughly analysed and processed with Pymol 2.3.0. The crystallographic waters were eliminated, and the crystallographic ligands were extracted and saved as individual files. To ensure consistent coordinates and docking conditions, all structures were aligned before performing the docking experiments. To assign Gasteiger charges and polar hydrogens to the proteins, Gold (2022.2 version) was used [27]. Then, a library of 3D structures of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde was created. The crystallographic ligands and aromatic aldehydes were prepared for docking using OpenBabel software and converted to mol2 [28]. Docking was performed on the LasR, PqsA, PqsE and PqsR proteins and the docking software used for this study was Gold (with the Goldscore scoring function) [29].

GoldScore is scoring function used in GOLD to rank the potential binding poses of a ligand to a protein. GOLD uses several scoring functions to evaluate the quality of the docking poses generated during the docking process. These scoring functions are mathematical models designed to predict the binding affinity between the ligand and the protein. In GoldScore, a higher score indicates a better binding pose suggesting a more favourable interaction between the ligand and the protein. Hence, a higher GoldScore is indicative of a stronger binding affinity. GoldScore, is the original scoring function provided with GOLD, is optimized for predicting the binding sites of the ligand, taking into account factors such as hydrogen bonds, van der Waals energy, metal interactions, and torsion deformations [30].

The defined parameters were the size of the anchor box, the definition of the binding site, the number of runs and the efficiency of the search. To validate the protocol, re-docking was performed by removing crystallographic ligands and re-docking them. This allows the user to assess the ability of the docking software and docking protocol to reproduce the geometry and orientation of the crystallographic pose [27]. Once the docking conditions were optimized, the benzaldehyde library of compounds was docked on the LasR, PqsA, PqsE and PqsR binding pockets. In addition, Maestro 13.6 (Schrödinger, LLC: New York, 2020) [31] was used to generate interaction maps to identify the major residues in the binding of benzaldehydes with the various proteins previously identified.

Table 2

Information of the X-ray structures of LasR, PqsA, PqsE and PqsR available in the PDB and BSD.

Protein	Code	Method	Ligand	Ligand Description	Description	Resolution (Å)	Mutation	Year	Ref.
LasR	2UV0	X-ray diffraction	OHN	Natural AI (3-oxo-C12-HSL)	Chains A (E), B (F), C (G), D (H)	1.80	0	2007	[32]
PqsA	5OE3	X-ray diffraction	3UK	inhibitor	Chains A, B, C, D	1.43	0	2017	[33]
PqsE	7TZA	X-ray diffraction	KYX	inhibitor	Chain A	2.10	0	2022	[34]
PqsR	6B8A	X-ray diffraction	CZG	inhibitor	Chains A, B	2.65	0	2018	[35]

2.6. Assessment of the inhibitory activity on QS-mediated virulence factors

2.6.1. Pyocyanin production

Extraction of pyocyanin from PA14-WT culture supernatants was performed according to the methodology described by Borges et al. [7]. Briefly, a suspension of PA14-WT ($OD_{600nm} = 0.05$) was grown at 37 °C and 150 rpm for 16 h in the presence of benzaldehydes at various concentrations (from 6.25 to 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). After the incubation period, the absorbance of the cultures was measured (at $\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$), and the cells were harvested by centrifugation (15 min at 3772 \times g). The resulting culture supernatant was collected. To extract pyocyanin, the culture supernatant was mixed with chloroform at a ratio of 3:5 (chloroform/supernatant). The lower blue chloroform layer was then transferred to a new tube and 1 mL of 0.2 M hydrochloric acid (HCl; Fisher Chemical, Merelbeke, Belgium) was added. The absorbance of the resulting top pink layer was measured at 520 nm using a microplate reader. To calculate the pyocyanin concentration in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, the absorbance ($\lambda = 520\text{ nm}$) values were multiplied by 17.072. Pyocyanin quantification was also performed for the PAO1-WT strain ($OD_{600nm} = 0.01$) after exposure to benzaldehydes (at 100, 400 and 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$).

2.6.2. Pyoverdine production

Pyoverdine production was quantified following the method described by Borges et al. [7]. The concentration of pyoverdine in the culture supernatant of *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT collected after benzaldehydes exposure was measured directly at 400 nm. To estimate relative pyoverdine production, the $A_{400\text{ nm}}$ values of the cultures were divided by their corresponding absorbance ($\lambda = 600\text{ nm}$) values.

2.7. Evaluation of the antibiofilm activity: benzaldehydes and antibiotics

2.7.1. Biofilm prevention

The prevention of *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145 biofilm formation by the benzaldehydes was evaluated according to Borges et al. [36]. Briefly, the OD ($\lambda = 620\text{ nm}$) of the bacterial cells was set to 0.04 ± 0.02 . Then, 180 μL of the bacterial suspension was added to clear-bottom PS 96-well microtiter plates with 20 μL of each benzaldehyde at the subinhibitory concentrations ($1/2 \times \text{MCT}$ and MCT). The microtiter plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h with agitation (150 rpm). Cell suspensions with DMSO and without benzaldehydes were used as negative controls.

2.7.2. Biofilm eradication

The effect of benzaldehydes on already established biofilms was carried out according to Baptista et al. [24]. Briefly, after overnight bacterial growth ($37 \pm 2\text{ °C}$ and 150 rpm in MHB), the OD ($\lambda = 620\text{ nm}$) was adjusted to 0.04 ± 0.02 . Then 96-well microtiter plates were filled with 200 μL /well of bacterial suspension and then incubated at 37 °C and 150 rpm for 24 h. After the biofilm formation step (24 h aged biofilms), the culture medium from each microtiter plate was replaced with 180 μL of fresh MHB and 20 μL of each benzaldehyde (MCT and $10 \times \text{MCT}$). Then the microtiter plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C with shaking (150 rpm). Cell suspensions with DMSO and without benzaldehydes were used as negative controls.

2.7.3. Quantification

After the incubation period, the content of each well was discarded and washed with a solution of sodium chloride (NaCl, 0.85 %) to remove non-adherent or weakly adherent bacterial cells. In addition, each well was neutralised for 15 min with universal neutraliser (30 g L^{-1} polysorbate 80 (VWR Chemicals, Le Havre, France), 30 g L^{-1} saponin (VWR Chemicals, Leuven, Belgium), 1 g L^{-1} L-histidine (Merck, Tokyo, Japan), 3 g L^{-1} lecithin (Alfa Aesar, Karlsruhe, Germany), 5 g L^{-1} sodium thiosulphate (Labkem, Barcelona, Spain) in 0.0025 M phosphate buffer [37]. The plates were analysed for total biomass by crystal violet (CV; Merck) staining, biofilm cells metabolic activity by alamar blue (AB,

Sigma-Aldrich) staining and biofilm culturable cells by colony forming unit (CFU) counts in solid medium.

2.7.3.1. Biomass. Quantification of biofilm mass was evaluated according to Borges et al. [36], by CV staining. The biofilm was firstly fixed with 250 μL of 99 % ethanol (Dipolar, Odivelas, Portugal) for 15 min. Then, the content of the microtiter plates was discarded, and the plates were dried at room temperature for 5 min. The fixed bacteria were then stained with 200 μL of a 1 % (v/v) CV solution for 5 min. The excess staining was carefully removed, and the dye-bound biomass was dissolved with 200 μL of 33 % (v/v) glacial acetic acid (Chem-Lab, Zedelgem, Belgium). Finally, absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microtiter plate reader.

The final results of the biofilm prevention assays were expressed as the percentage of biomass production reduction (%BPR), which were calculated according to the following equation (1):

$$\%BPR = \frac{OD_{cp} - OD_{wp}}{OD_{cp}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where OD_{cp} represents the OD value ($\lambda = 570\text{ nm}$) of the biofilms formed by bacterial cells not exposed to benzaldehydes and OD_{wp} is the OD value ($\lambda = 570\text{ nm}$) for biofilms formed by bacterial cells in the presence of benzaldehydes.

Regarding to biofilm eradication assays, the results were expressed as the percentage of biomass removal (%BR) after exposure to the compounds and calculated according to the following equation (2):

$$\%BR = \frac{OD_{ce} - OD_{we}}{OD_c} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where OD_{ce} is the OD value ($\lambda = 570\text{ nm}$) of the 24 h old biofilms not exposed to benzaldehydes and OD_{we} is the OD value ($\lambda = 570\text{ nm}$) of 24 h old biofilms exposed to benzaldehydes.

2.7.3.2. Biofilm cells metabolic activity. The quantification of the metabolic activity of biofilm cells was evaluated according to Borges et al. [22] by staining with AB or resazurin (7-hydroxy-3H-phenoxazin-3-one-10-oxide). This process is based on the conversion of resazurin (originally blue and non-fluorescent) by metabolically active cells into resorufin, which emits pink fluorescence upon reduction [38]. For this, 190 μL of fresh MHB medium and 10 μL of AB indicator solution (at 0.4 mM) prepared in sterile distilled water were added to each well of the microtiter plate. The plates were then incubated for 4 h in the dark and at 37 °C. Finally, fluorescence measurement (λ excitation = 570 nm and λ emission = 590 nm) was performed in a microtiter plate reader.

The final results of the biofilm prevention assays were expressed as the percentage of metabolic activity reduction (%MAR), which were calculated according to the following equation (3):

$$\%MAR = \frac{FL_{cp} - FL_{wp}}{FL_{cp}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where FL_{cp} is the fluorescence intensity value of the biofilms formed by bacterial cells not exposed to benzaldehydes and FL_{wp} is the fluorescence intensity value for biofilms formed by bacterial cells in the presence of benzaldehydes.

Regarding to biofilm eradication assays, the final results were expressed as the percentage of biofilm cells metabolic activity reduction (%BMAR) after exposure to the compounds and calculated according to the following equation (4):

$$\%BMAR = \frac{FL_{ce} - FL_{we}}{FL_{ce}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

FL_c is the fluorescence intensity of the biofilm cells not exposed to benzaldehydes and FL_{we} is the fluorescence intensity of biofilm cells exposed to benzaldehydes.

2.7.3.3. Biofilm culturable cells. The culturability of biofilm cells was analysed according to Borges et al. [36]. Biofilm cells were collected by scraping the microtiter plate wells three times (each time for 1 min) and resuspended in 200 μL of sterile NaCl. The contents of each well were transferred to sterile microcentrifuge tubes. Then a 10-fold serial dilution was performed with NaCl and 10 μL of each dilution was plated in PCA plates. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The number of CFU was visually counted ($10 < \text{CFU} < 200$) and expressed per square centimetre of the microtiter plate well (CFU cm^{-2}), according to the following equations (5) and (6):

$$\frac{\text{CFU}}{\text{mL}} = \frac{N}{\text{SV} \times \text{Dilution}} \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of CFU on the PCA plates and SV is the sample volume in mL.

$$\frac{\text{CFU}}{\text{cm}^2} = \frac{\frac{\text{CFU}}{\text{mL}} \times \text{WV}}{\text{Wa}} \quad (6)$$

where WV is the working volume of the well (0.2 mL), and Wa is the area of the well in cm^2 (1.53).

2.8. Evaluation of the antibiofilm activity: benzaldehyde-antibiotic combinations

The combined effect of each selected benzaldehyde with the antibiotics ciprofloxacin or tobramycin was investigated in *P. aeruginosa* biofilm control (prevention and eradication studies). For this purpose, a similar procedure as described in sections 2.7.1 and 2.7.2 was used, with minor changes in the concentration and volume of the compounds [24]. For the prevention experiments, 10 μL of each benzaldehyde (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde in $1/2 \times \text{MCT}$), 10 μL of ciprofloxacin (at $1/64 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$ and $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$)/tobramycin (at $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$ and $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$) and 180 μL of bacterial suspension were used. Regarding the biofilm eradication assays, 10 μL of each benzaldehyde (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde in $10 \times \text{MCT}$), 10 μL of ciprofloxacin (in $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$ and $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$)/tobramycin (in $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$ and $1/4 \times \text{MIC}$) and 180 μL of MHB were applied to already formed biofilms. Cell suspensions with DMSO and without benzaldehydes/antibiotics were used as negative controls. After the incubation period, the biofilms were examined for biomass, metabolic activity and culturability, as described in 2.7.3.1., 2.7.3.2. and 2.7.3.3., respectively.

The interaction between benzaldehydes and ciprofloxacin/tobramycin was evaluated using the Σ Combinatorial Index (ΣC_i) defined on the basis of the score proposed by Baptista et al. [24]. The Combinatorial Index of benzaldehydes ($C_{i|A|D}$) was calculated according to equation (7):

$$C_{i|A|D} = \frac{RE_{ALD}}{RE_{ALD|A}} \quad (7)$$

where RE_{ALD} corresponds to the results obtained for benzaldehydes alone for each method [%BPR, %BR, %MAR, %BMAR or $\log(\text{CFU cm}^{-2})$ reduction] and $RE_{ALD|A}$ corresponds to the results obtained for the combination of benzaldehydes and antibiotic (ciprofloxacin or tobramycin) for each method.

The Antibiotic Combinatorial Index ($C_{i|A}$) was evaluated in a similar manner. Subsequently, the sum of $C_{i|A|D}$ and $C_{i|A}$ equates to ΣC_i , as given in equation (8):

$$\Sigma C_i = C_{i|A|D} + C_{i|A} \quad (8)$$

The calculated ΣC_i values were subsequently categorized based on the interaction between benzaldehydes and antibiotics (ciprofloxacin/tobramycin) against *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145 biofilms:

- Less than 0.5 indicates a synergistic effect (+++).

- Between 0.5 and 2 means an additive effect (++).
- In the range of 2–4 is categorized as indifferent (+).
- Above 4 means an antagonistic effect (–).

2.9. Evaluation of the susceptibility of biofilms formed in the presence of benzaldehydes to antibiotics

To test the effect of benzaldehydes on biofilm susceptibility to ciprofloxacin and tobramycin [4], biofilms were developed in the presence of benzaldehydes at a concentration of $1/2 \times \text{MCT}$. Cell suspensions with DMSO and without benzaldehydes were used as negative controls. After 24 h incubation at 37 °C and 150 rpm, the 24 h old biofilms were washed with NaCl and treated with ciprofloxacin and tobramycin at a concentration of $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$ and $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$, respectively. The plates were incubated at 37 °C and 150 rpm for an additional 24 h. Then biofilms were analysed for biomass, metabolic activity and culturability as described in previous 2.7.3.1., 2.7.3.2. and 2.7.3.3., respectively.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism software version 8 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Significance was tested using one-way comparisons ANOVA and multiple comparisons based on $\geq 95\%$ confidence level ($p < 0.05$, statistically significant). All experiments were conducted in duplicate with at least three replicates for each condition tested.

3. Results and discussion

The excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics combined with the natural adaptability of bacteria has led to an increasing resistance of these microorganisms [13]. Bacterial resistance is a particular concern when the bacteria form biofilms, where the colonizer cells are particularly recalcitrant to antibiotics and the immune system [39]. Currently, there are no effective drugs or treatments to combat bacterial biofilms [40]. The use of QSI is becoming increasingly important in combating severe bacterial infections [14]. This is due to their ability to neutralise virulent bacteria and thus reduce their pathogenicity in the host. Moreover, this strategy allows the interference with the formation and stability of biofilms and thus disrupts the protective environment causing antibiotic resistance [11]. This approach reduces the strong selective pressure on the antibacterial effect of antibiotics, that would kill bacteria or inhibit their growth [41].

In this study, natural molecules (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde) as inhibitors of two QS systems and the production of virulence factors by *P. aeruginosa* were tested. In addition, the combination of the benzaldehydes with ciprofloxacin and tobramycin was investigated in biofilm control as adjuvants to boost their efficacy.

3.1. Antibacterial activity of benzaldehydes and antibiotics

The inhibitory (MIC) and bactericidal (MBC) activities of the benzaldehydes were evaluated to determine the appropriate concentrations for QS inhibition assays. The MIC and MBC values obtained for the benzaldehydes 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde, as well as for the antibiotics ciprofloxacin and tobramycin against *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145 are shown in Table 3. No inhibitory or bactericidal activity was observed up to 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (the MCT, for all the benzaldehydes). However, an MIC and MBC value of 32 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were recorded for ciprofloxacin, while tobramycin had a MIC and MBC of 8 and 16 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, respectively. In addition, the MIC and MBC of the benzaldehydes were investigated for the strains PA14-WT, PA14-R3, PAO1-WT and PAO1-CTX (Supplementary information; Table S1). The same result was obtained with MIC and MBC values of more than 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for these *P. aeruginosa* strains. This could be related to the low concentrations used compared to other studies, or to different

Table 3
MIC and MBC values of benzaldehydes for *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 10145.

Compound	Chemical structure	MIC ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	MBC ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde		>1000	>1000
Vanillin		>1000	>1000
Syringaldehyde		>1000	>1000
Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride		32	32
Tobramycin		8	16

P. aeruginosa strains. For example, Kim et al. [42] showed that for *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 the MIC obtained for vanillin was $5000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde was $1250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. An important aspect that should be taken into account is for which application a compound is intended to be used. For instance, vanillin is already used in the food industry at a concentration of 131 mM ($\approx 20000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) [16]. This underscores its safety with possibly low toxicity in humans. However, the assessment of safety takes on a different perspective when considering clinical applications.

Considering the obtained results, for the QS assessment experiments, $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was used as the highest concentration.

3.2. Effect of benzaldehydes on *P. aeruginosa* QS systems

3.2.1. Effect on the *las* system

The *las* system is one of the most important among the different *P. aeruginosa* QS pathways known, as it mediates the expression of the *rhl*, *pqs* and *iqs* systems [3]. This QS pathway uses 3-oxo-C12-HSL as AI, with LasI being the synthase protein and LasR the receptor [43]. When *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3 recognises 3-oxo-C12-HSL synthesised by *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT, this leads to the emission of bioluminescence. In this way, a promising inhibitor is a compound able to reduce bioluminescence by at least 50 % without significantly affecting cell growth (<20 %) [44]. It is important that bacterial growth is not affected to minimise the non-specific effects of impaired growth on the QS response [44]. The benzaldehydes 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde have MICs higher than $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, demonstrating their ineffectiveness in inhibiting the growth of different strains of *P. aeruginosa*. The results of the QS inhibition screening performed for all aromatic aldehydes at sub-MICs ($6.25\text{--}1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) are shown in Fig. 1 (furvina and FC30 were used as controls - Fig. S1). The three benzaldehydes inhibited the *P. aeruginosa* 3-oxo-C12-HSL QS system, and the effect was dose-dependent. Vanillin was the most effective, with a reduction of 86 % in bioluminescence at a concentration of $400 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, without affecting bacterial growth (Fig. 1B).

4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (at $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and syringaldehyde (at $400 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) reduced the bioluminescence by 63 % and 73 %, respectively. The most significant percentages of reduction in bioluminescence were obtained at the highest concentrations tested (800 and $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). However, it was also verified that bacterial growth was strongly affected, especially with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde ($>100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Although no MIC values were found for the range of concentrations tested, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde at 800 and $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ affected considerably the cell growth of *P. aeruginosa* strains after 24 h of incubation (Figs. S2–S4). Therefore, depending on the concentration, the benzaldehydes tested can be considered promising inhibitors that disrupt QS without impairing cell growth.

3.2.1.1. Effect on the production and response of AIs. The QSIs can demonstrate their efficacy across three main levels, including the synthesis, transport, and detection of AIs [39]. Therefore, additional studies were conducted to infer the inherent mode of action of the benzaldehydes on the 3-oxo-C12-HSL-dependent QS system of *P. aeruginosa*, involving the production and/or detection of 3-oxo-C12-HSL (Fig. 2 and Figs. S5–S8). It was found that the benzaldehydes under study were able to inhibit the emission of bioluminescence by the PA14-R3 strain cultured in the presence of exogenously added 3-oxo-C12-HSL (interference on the AIs detection) by 20 % (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde at $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to 30 % (syringaldehyde at $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2). With respect to the effect on AIs production, after quantification of the amount of 3-oxo-C12-HSL produced by PA14-WT in the presence of benzaldehydes and detected by PA-R3, only a slight decrease was observed (Fig. S6). Regarding bioluminescence, a maximum decrease of 25 % was obtained for vanillin at $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (Fig. S7). Therefore, the benzaldehydes have a subtle influence on the detection of 3-oxo-C12-HSL through the interference with its synthesis.

3.2.2. Effect on the *pqs* system

Bacterial QS systems often interact with each other mutually influencing their regulatory activities in the cell [3]. This cross-system

Fig. 1. - Effect of increasing concentrations of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (A), vanillin (B) and syringaldehyde (C) (6.25–1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) on the *P. aeruginosa* 3-oxo-C12-HSL-dependent QS system (primary y - axis; bars) and growth inhibition ($\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$, secondary y - axis; line), ne = no effect. Bioluminescence emissions were normalised to the cell density of the bacterial culture and expressed as a percentage with respect to the untreated controls (cells + DMSO at 1 %, relative bioluminescence). Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated.

Fig. 2. - Effect of increasing concentrations of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (A), vanillin (B) and syringaldehyde (C) (6.25–1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) on the detection of 3-oxo-C12-HSL (primary y - axis; bars) and growth inhibition ($\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$, secondary y - axis; line) of *P. aeruginosa* PA14-R3. Bioluminescence emissions were normalised to the cell density of the bacterial culture and expressed as a percentage with respect to the untreated controls (cells + DMSO at 1 %, relative bioluminescence). Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated.

regulation allows *P. aeruginosa* to synchronise its behaviour and adapt to changing environments [45]. The protein LasR performs a central role in this regulatory network and interacts with the other QS systems of *P. aeruginosa*. When activated, LasR is responsible for the positive regulation of the *las* system (LasI), the *rhl* system (RhlI and RhlR) and the *pqs* system (PqsR and PqsH) [45,46]. Interestingly, the regulatory landscape of the *P. aeruginosa* QS system also includes negative regulation. For instance, the *rhl* system, negatively regulates the *pqs* system [46]. In turn, PqsR, when activated, serves as a transcriptional activator for PqsABCDEH and RhlR [47]. This coordination may explain why inhibition of the *las* system, the top of the hierarchy of *P. aeruginosa* QS systems, may not be sufficient to suppress virulence. For example, Soto-Aceves et al. [48] showed that strains of *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 with mutations in the LasR protein do not suppress the expression of virulence factors. This demonstrates that the hierarchical arrangement of the QS systems can be flexible. In particular, Maura and colleagues [49] propose that the hierarchical regulatory model of *P. aeruginosa* QS systems should consist of a circular model interconnected by *las*, *rhl* and *pqs* systems. This is consistent with the fact that there is a high reduction in the initial screening tests concerning the global effect on the *las* system (Fig. 1) and a moderate influence in the production and detection assays (Fig. 2, S6 and S7). In this way, the effect of the selected benzaldehydes was investigated in other QS systems of *P. aeruginosa*, namely in the *pqs* system.

The *pqs* system, mediated by AIs from the quinolone family, also plays an important role in the pathogenic behaviour of *P. aeruginosa* [50, 51]. This system uses 4-hydroxy-2-heptylquinoline (HHQ) and 3,4-dihydroxy-2-heptylquinoline (PQS) as a signalling molecule recognized by the transcriptional regulator PqsR (also known as MvR) [18,41]. The PqsABCD are proteins involved in the synthesis of HHQ, which is converted to PQS via PqsH [47]. PqsE acts as a thioesterase in the biosynthesis of alkylquinolones and controls the expression of virulence factors

via a mechanism that is not well understood yet [52]. In fact, PqsE is associated with the regulation of pyocyanin levels and iron acquisition through the regulation of siderophores [41]. Furthermore, Allesen-Holm and colleagues [53] showed that biofilms formed by *pqsA* mutants contained less extracellular DNA than biofilms formed by *P. aeruginosa* PAO1-WT. This suggests that eDNA production is regulated by the *pqs* system in *P. aeruginosa*. Furthermore, the *pqs* system may help to increase the resistance of bacteria to environmental stress by promoting their fitness through changes in the architecture of the biofilm [52]. In this way, the *pqs* system is crucial for the virulence and biofilm formation of *P. aeruginosa* and is involved in several processes, including iron acquisition pathways, virulence factor production, eDNA production, outer membrane vesicle biogenesis and the host immune response [41, 46,54].

Despite the recognized *pqs* inhibition activity of vanillin, to the authors' knowledge, *pqs* inhibition potential has never been evaluated for the other two structurally related benzaldehydes (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and syringaldehyde).

P. aeruginosa PAO1-WT and PAO1-CTX were used to evaluate the inhibitory effect of this type of benzaldehydes in the *pqs* system [18]. The results obtained are shown in Fig. 3 (concentrations of 100, 400 and 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were evaluated, since 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was the initial concentration that caused a 50 % reduction in bioluminescence in the first screening tests). As expected, vanillin (at 400 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) leads to a 62 % reduction in the bioluminescence of the PAO1-CTX and reaches a maximum reduction of 79 % (at 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), without affecting bacterial growth (Fig. 3B). Similar results were obtained by Mok et al. [16], who found that vanillin reduced *pqsA*-gfp GFP levels at a concentration of ≈ 4 mM (608 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) using the PAO1- WT/PqsA-gfp transcriptional fusion biosensor complex. Furthermore, the authors suggest that vanillin may inhibit the PqsR response protein rather than PQS biosynthesis. Syringaldehyde, in turn, decreased bioluminescence

Fig. 3. - Effect of increasing concentrations of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (A), vanillin (B) and syringaldehyde (C) (100, 400 and 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) on the *pqs* system of *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 (primary y - axis; bars) and growth inhibition ($\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$; secondary y-axis; line), ne = no effect. Bioluminescence emissions were normalised to the cell density of the bacterial culture and expressed as a percentage with respect to the untreated controls (cells + DMSO at 1 %, relative bioluminescence). Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated.

by 57 % without affecting cell growth, suggesting its potential as a promising QSI agent. On the other hand, while 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde reduced bioluminescence by 81 %, it also severely impaired bacterial growth (ca. 81 % of growth inhibition). Thus, this compound does not fit the premise of a promising QSI, as its activity could be mostly related to the inhibition of cell growth. To validate the QSI potential of aromatic aldehydes, *in silico* studies were conducted.

3.3. Validation of the QS inhibition activity of benzaldehydes by *in silico* approaches

Computational approaches were employed to validate the *in vitro* screenings and uncover possible binding modes of benzaldehydes within different protein pockets in the *las* and *pqs* systems. Therefore, molecular docking was performed for the benzaldehydes in the proteins LasR, PqsA, PqsE and PqsR. In addition, key residue analysis was conducted for selected benzaldehyde recognition. The results of the docking scores are shown in Fig. 4 and S9, where a comparison of the scores of two different proteins (LasR with PqsR and PqsA with PqsE) was made. Moreover, the scores consisting of Goldscore values were normalised per heavy atom. Seemingly, the aromatic aldehydes for both proteins studied have better scores compared to their reference ligands, with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde giving the best result.

This can be explained by the low molecular weight that the benzaldehydes have, when compared to the reference ligands and relatively high docking score. It can also be observed that the benzaldehydes give a better result for the LasR protein, in comparison with the PqsR protein (Fig. 4). This could indicate that aromatic aldehydes are more likely to interact with LasR than with PqsR.

Additionally, benzaldehydes demonstrated a higher docking score when interacting with PqsE compared to PqsA (Fig. S9). This is consistent with the fact that benzaldehydes show an effective reduction in pyocyanin levels, as PqsE is closely associated with the production of

this virulence factor [41].

Using Pymol 2.3.0., it was observed that the benzaldehydes can bind to the active site of LasR (Fig. 5), PqsR (Fig. S10), PqsA (Fig. S11) and PqsE (Fig. S12), in the same pocket as their reference ligands. For example, the simulations of the LasR protein showed that the benzaldehydes have a similar binding mode and pose as the 3-oxo-C12-HSL (natural AI). With respect to the PqsR pocket, the existence of 2 sub-domains was demonstrated (Fig. S10).

This is consistent with the study of Vieira et al. [27], who showed that the PqsR binding pocket has two subdomains, referred to as pockets A and B. In this sense, it was verified that 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde tends to be stable in pocket A, where the bicyclic ring of the natural AI fits.

Vanillin and syringaldehyde, in turn, are docked into pocket B, in a similar manner to the aliphatic chain of the reference ligand. This aligns with the higher score for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde since it effectively fits into the active site of the reference ligand (CZG). A similar effect was also observed for PqsA, as this protein has a U-shaped pocket [33] (Fig. S11). In this sense, the preferred position of syringaldehyde is in the adenine ring-binding pocket in anthranlyoyl-AMP, while the other two benzaldehydes tend to be positioned on the opposite site. Similar dispositions to the reference ligand were observed for the benzaldehydes in the PqsE structures (Fig. S12).

A more detailed description of the binding mode of benzaldehydes in the proteins LasR (Fig. 6), PqsR (Fig. S13), PqsA (Fig. S14), and PqsE (Fig. S15), was evaluated. Thus, syringaldehyde, although having a much lower molecular weight than AI, was shown to form hydrogen bonds with the residues Arg-61 and Tyr-56. The bond with the Tyr-56 residue is extremely important for ligand recognition. 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin establish a van der Waals interaction with the Leu-110 residue and π - π stacking with the Trp-88 and Phe-101 residues. This suggests that these two benzaldehydes have very similar properties. For example, in Bottomley et al. [32], a total of 6 hydrogen bonds were observed between natural AI and the LasR residues Tyr-56, Trp-60,

Fig. 4. -2D graphical representation of docking scores of PqsR vs LasR for reference ligand of PqsR (CZG), reference ligand of LasR (OHN - 3-oxo-C12-HSL), 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin, and syringaldehyde. The result was normalised per heavy atoms and the size of the plots is directly proportional to their molecular weight.

Fig. 5. - Position of the natural ligand of LasR (OHN) (A). Hypothetical position of the benzaldehydes 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (B), vanillin (C), and syringaldehyde (D) in LasR pocket. Surface representation of 2UV0 and identification of the pocket shape by a vertical section of the protein (figure produced using Pymol 2.3.0.).

Arg-61, Asp-73, Thr-75 and Ser-129. In this way, it can be established that the selected benzaldehydes tend to form bonds with the residues of the LasR protein similar to those of the 3-oxo-C12-HSL. As shown earlier for PqsR, the benzaldehydes only occupy a portion of the pocket. For example, vanillin and syringaldehyde (in pocket B) form a van der Waals interaction with Ile-236, which is one of the most important residues when interacting with natural AI [27]. 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde can form π - π interactions with Tyr-258 and a van der Waals interaction with Leu-183 (Fig. S13).

For PqsA, hydrogen bonds were detected with residue Thr-323 for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and Asp-299 for syringaldehyde (Fig. S14). In addition, van der Waals interactions were observed in this protein with residues Gly-279 for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, Gly-307 and Gly-302 for vanillin, and with Gly-279 for syringaldehyde (Fig. S14). These interactions may be significant as they indicate the possibility of competition for the binding site with the natural ligand. Chen et al. [55] found that mutants for residues Gly-279 and Asp-299 significantly weakened the binding between the ligand and the PqsA protein. They also verified that norharman (the QSI identified by the authors) has an inhibitory effect on PqsA and establishes hydrogen bonds with these residues. These authors also found that the inhibition by norharman occurred through competition with anthranilyl-AMP at the active site.

Finally, regarding PqsE, benzaldehydes also tend to stabilise in the pocket through hydrogen bonds with specific residues, Asp-73 and His-71 for syringaldehyde and vanillin, and with residue Glu-182 for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Fig. S15).

3.4. Effect of the benzaldehydes in the production of virulence factors

The influence of the *las* and *pqs* systems on the pathogenicity/virulence of *P. aeruginosa* is mainly due to their ability to regulate the production of virulence factors and biofilm formation [39]. *P. aeruginosa* can produce several virulence factors (e.g. exotoxins, pyocyanin, proteases, phospholipases, alginate, siderophores, flagellins, lipopolysaccharide) that are critical to its ability to initiate and establish infections, evade the host immune response, and damage host tissues [56,57].

Pyocyanin is a small molecule with redox activity produced by *P. aeruginosa* at high cell density in response to *las*, *rhl* and *pqs* [57]. Pyocyanin is not only a terminal signalling factor in the QS network, but also a molecule that facilitates bacterial penetration into biological host membranes due to its zwitterionic properties [58]. Furthermore, this extracellular molecule leads to increased host cell cytotoxicity through its ability to induce oxidative stress (by increasing intracellular reactive oxygen species and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) concentration) [58]. In addition, pyocyanin induces neutrophil apoptosis, inflammatory responses, and neutrophil-mediated tissue damage [7]. The effect of the benzaldehydes in reducing the amount of pyocyanin was estimated in relation to the negative control (cells and 1 % DMSO). The benzaldehydes caused a subtle reduction of the pyocyanin level, especially at the highest concentrations, as shown in Fig. 7. The maximum reduction was achieved for vanillin, showing a reduction of 48 % at a concentration of $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. In addition, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde also revealed promise, attaining a reduction of ca. 42 % at $400 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, but cell growth was also affected. In turn, at a concentration of $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde displayed a reduction of 31 % without affecting

Fig. 6. - Interaction map of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (A), vanillin (B), and syringaldehyde (C) in the LasR pocket together with important residues of ligand recognition and their distances (figure produced using Maestro 13.6 software).

the cell growth of *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT (Fig. 7A). Syringaldehyde showed a maximum percentage of reduction of 38 % (at 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). The effect of this type of aldehydes was higher than that of furvina (25 %) and FC30 (36 %), which were used as positive controls (Fig. S16). This is in agreement with the data of Borges et al. [4], who showed that furvina only reduced a maximum of 20 % at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The pyocyanin content in the supernatants of the *P. aeruginosa* PAO1-WT strain was also investigated (Fig. S17). The same trend as for strain *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT was observed, with a reduction of 43 % for vanillin (at 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), 37 % for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (at 400 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and 27 % for syringaldehyde (at 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$).

P. aeruginosa also can secrete molecules with a high affinity for iron, called siderophores. These molecules are produced to increase the accumulation of iron in bacteria from the surrounding environment [59]. Pyoverdine and pyochelin are a type of siderophores produced by

P. aeruginosa, and are extremely important in promoting bacterial growth as well as virulence [56]. The use of QSI to suppress siderophore secretion is receiving increasing attention and may be critical for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa*-related infections. Thus, the interference of benzaldehydes on pyoverdine production by PA14-WT cells was investigated. The results are shown in Fig. S18. The effect of benzaldehydes was calculated in relation to the cell suspension in the presence of 1 % DMSO. No reduction in the pyoverdine content was observed for aromatic aldehydes, regardless of the concentration tested (Figs. S18 and S19).

3.5. Effects of benzaldehydes in combination with ciprofloxacin/tobramycin on biofilm control

The use of QSI can be a good “ally” to improve or restore the effect of

Fig. 7. - Influence of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (A), vanillin (B) and syringaldehyde (C) on pyocyanin production (primary y - axis; bars) and growth inhibition (OD_{600nm} , secondary y - axis; line) as a function of the different concentrations (6.25–1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). The levels of pyocyanin were measured in cell free supernatants ($\lambda = 520 \text{ nm}$) from cultures of the *P. aeruginosa* PA14-WT strain. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated.

less effective antibiotics in the treatment of bacterial infections as the combination of QSI and antibiotics may allow the use of lower doses and avoid the misuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics [60]. In addition, could the use of this type of adjuvants can shorten the duration of treatment and avoid the combined use of several antibiotics, thereby avoiding complications associated with their use [61]. In fact, QS systems can play a fundamental role in coordinating the expression of resistance genes and thus contribute to an organised response of bacteria against the action of antibiotics [62]. In addition, QS may be responsible for the activation of resistance strategies such as efflux pumps and enzyme inactivation [49,62]. On the other hand, QS is closely related to the formation and maintenance of biofilms, which increase recalcitrance to antibiotics and make treatment even more difficult [39].

To evaluate the effect of QSI in combination with antibiotics, an initial screening was performed for six antibiotics from different classes (aminoglycosides – tobramycin and gentamicin; third-generation cephalosporins - ceftazidime; fourth-generation cephalosporins - cefepime, quinolones - ciprofloxacin, and tetracycline) using the disc diffusion test (Table S2). Although all combinations resulted in an indifferent effect, a slight increase in IZD was observed with the combination of tobramycin with all the benzaldehydes, as well as with the combination of ciprofloxacin with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Table S2). In this sense, combinations of the benzaldehydes with ciprofloxacin/tobramycin were prepared and evaluated in the formation and eradication of biofilms and scored according to the Σ CI. Finally, the susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* biofilms previously formed in the presence of QSI to ciprofloxacin and tobramycin was also assessed.

3.5.1. Effect on prevention of biofilm formation

To evaluate the biofilm preventive effects, benzaldehydes at 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and antibiotics at subinhibitory concentrations (tobramycin: 1/32

\times MIC, 1/16 \times MIC, 1/8 \times MIC, 1/4 \times MIC; ciprofloxacin: 1/64 \times MIC, 1/32 \times MIC, 1/16 \times MIC, 1/8 \times MIC) were used. It was found that the benzaldehydes alone were able to reduce the biofilm mass production by 15–30 %, with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde showing the greatest reduction (Fig. 8).

The observed decrease in biomass production could be related to several effects at the level of the biofilm matrix. For instance, Si et al. [63] investigated the ability of vanillin to prevent biofilm formation in a mixed microbial culture (*Comamonas*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Pseudomonas*, *Stenotrophomonas*, *Nakamurella*, *Clostridium*, *Azospira*, *Sphingomonas* and *Ferribacterium*). Using confocal laser microscopy, the authors demonstrated that exposure of mixed biofilms to vanillin (at 300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) resulted in a significant decrease in the content of exoproteins and exopolysaccharides in the biofilm matrix. In contrast, the untreated biofilms presented large amounts of exoproteins and exopolysaccharides on the cell surfaces of the biofilms.

Regarding antibiotics, ciprofloxacin had no effect when 1/64 \times MIC was applied, and the same result was obtained for tobramycin at 1/32 \times MIC and 1/16 \times MIC. The results are in accordance with the study by Hoffman et al. [64], which found that antibiotics from the aminoglycoside class, when administered in subinhibitory concentrations, promote biofilm formation rather than preventing it. Specifically, the authors found that biofilm mass reached a maximum increase when incubated with 0.3 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of tobramycin compared to untreated *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 cells. In addition, the authors also observed a rise in CFU, suggesting that the subinhibitory concentrations of aminoglycoside antibiotics cause an increase in cell number rather than an increase in the extracellular matrix.

P. aeruginosa biomass production was reduced by more than 50 % with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde combined with 1/16 \times MIC of tobramycin (61 % BPR). This result showed the significant effect of this aldehyde in

Fig. 8. - Preventive action of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes, as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of biomass production. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with “*” are statistically different from tobramycin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ne = no effect, ns = non-significant.

potentiating the outcome of the antibiotic, as tobramycin alone showed no reduction. When vanillin and syringaldehyde were combined with a $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$ of tobramycin, a maximum reduction of 48 % and 28 %, respectively, was achieved (Fig. 8A). Similarly, when 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde were combined with $1/64 \times \text{MIC}$ of ciprofloxacin, a reduction of 44 %, 16 % and 15 %, respectively, was observed (Fig. 8b), while ciprofloxacin alone had no effect.

In terms of metabolic activity, all the benzaldehydes displayed an inhibitory effect of less than 20 %. However, their combined application with tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) showed an enhanced effect, with syringaldehyde presenting an increase of almost 40 % compared to the use of the antibiotic alone (Fig. 9A). Similar results were obtained with ciprofloxacin (at $1/64 \times \text{MIC}$; reduction of about 20 %), where its application combined with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde achieved the greatest activity with a reduction of 69 % (Fig. 9B).

At the culturability level, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin in

combination with tobramycin achieved reductions in the order of 1.7 and 1.1 log (CFU cm^{-2}), respectively (Fig. 10A). In contrast, the combination of benzaldehydes with ciprofloxacin achieved a reduction of 1.6 log (CFU cm^{-2}) (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde-ciprofloxacin combination) (Fig. 10B).

Regarding the Combinatorial Index ($\sum \text{CI}$), the analysis revealed that the majority of interactions between benzaldehydes and ciprofloxacin/tobramycin were additive, as shown in Table S3. Synergistic interactions were observed in terms of BPR for the combinations of vanillin with tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) and ciprofloxacin (at $1/64 \times \text{MIC}$). In terms of culturability, the combination of vanillin and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde with tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) reached a synergistic effect, as well as for the combination of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde with ciprofloxacin (at $1/64 \times \text{MIC}$).

On the other hand, antagonistic interactions were observed with vanillin and syringaldehyde in combination with tobramycin (at $1/32 \times$

Fig. 9. – Preventive action of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes, as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of metabolic activity. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with “*” are statistically different from tobramycin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ne = no effect, ns = non-significant.

MIC and $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$, respectively) in reducing mass production. In the case of the combination of syringaldehyde with tobramycin (at $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$), an antagonistic effect was observed, impacting both biomass production and culturability reduction.

3.5.2. Effects on the pre-established biofilms

The importance of QS in mature biofilms lies mainly in its ability to regulate the production of virulence factors that promote the survival and persistence of the biofilm community [65,66]. Therefore, the use of QSI will help to destabilise the cohesion of the biofilm and reduce the virulence of the bacteria.

The results of the effect of the benzaldehydes on mature biofilms and of antibiotics and their combinations are described in Figs. 11–13. Different concentrations of antibiotics were used for these tests, including three subinhibitory concentrations and one inhibitory

concentration of tobramycin ($1/16 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/4 \times \text{MIC}$ and $5/2 \times \text{MIC}$) and ciprofloxacin ($1/32 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$, $1/8 \times \text{MIC}$, and $5/4 \times \text{MIC}$). The individual use of the benzaldehydes showed promising biomass removal effects, with vanillin (at $10000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) achieving a 40 % reduction.

This effect can be ascribed to vanillin ability to reduce the content of exopolysaccharides and exoproteins, as stated previously. However, the combination of vanillin with tobramycin or ciprofloxacin had no better effect than benzaldehyde alone. The combination of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde with tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) and ciprofloxacin (at $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$) resulted in a biomass removal of 24 % and 20 %, respectively, compared to the antibiotics alone (Fig. 11A and B). Similar effects were observed with syringaldehyde, where its combination with ciprofloxacin ($1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) achieved a reduction of 51 %.

As for metabolic activity, all phytochemicals in this study showed a

Fig. 10. - Preventive action of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes, as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of culturable cells [log (CFU cm⁻²)]. Mean values ± standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with '*' are statistically different from ciprofloxacin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ns = non-significant. Bars with lowercase letters are statistically different from the control (biofilms without treatment and exposed to DMSO at 1% or 0.5%) for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$, where a = ns and b = ****).

reduction of about 65 % when applied individually at a concentration of 10000 µg mL⁻¹. Furthermore, combinations of the benzaldehydes and antibiotics resulted in a 90 % reduction at all concentrations tested (Fig. 12).

Of note, tobramycin showed no reduction when applied at a concentration of 1/16 × MIC and a 48 % reduction when tested at a concentration of 1/8 × MIC (Fig. 12A). Ciprofloxacin showed a strong decrease in biofilm metabolic activity (at all concentrations), as shown in Fig. 12B. This reduction may be attributed to the ability of this antibiotic to inhibit vital enzymes known as topoisomerase II (or DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which play a crucial role in bacterial DNA replication [67]. As a result, it can lead to disruption of DNA replication, damage to genetic material and inhibition of protein synthesis, culminating in suppression of bacterial metabolic activity.

In terms of biofilm culturability, when applied alone, only vanillin (at 10000 µg mL⁻¹) showed positive results with 2.5 log (CFU cm⁻²)

reduction compared to the control (cells incubated with 5 % DMSO). The most remarkable results were obtained with the benzaldehyde-tobramycin combinations, where a reduction of ca. 2.2 log (CFU cm⁻²) was observed for 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin in combination compared to tobramycin alone (at 1/16 × MIC) (Fig. 13A). This trend was also observed with ciprofloxacin (at 1/32 × MIC and 1/16 × MIC), but only around 0.6 log (CFU cm⁻²) of reduction was observed when 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin were combined with ciprofloxacin (Fig. 13B).

The results obtained are consistent with the findings of Anderson et al. [68] who demonstrated the efficacy of the combination of tobramycin and fosfomycin against preformed biofilms of *P. aeruginosa*. Although the outcome was slightly higher (about 3 log (CFU cm⁻²) reduction), high concentrations of tobramycin (12.8 µg mL⁻¹) and fosfomycin (51.2 µg mL⁻¹) were used. In the present study, not only a natural compound was used instead of an antibiotic, but the

Fig. 11. – Effect of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes, as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against pre-established 24 h old *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of biomass removal. The bottom panels in A and B show photographs of wells from the 96-well microtiter plate assay with crystal violet of tobramycin and ciprofloxacin combined with benzaldehydes. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with “*” are statistically different from tobramycin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ns = non-significant.

Fig. 12. - Effect of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes, as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against pre-established 24 h old *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of biofilm cells metabolic activity. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with '*' are statistically different from tobramycin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ne = no effect.

combinations with the benzaldehydes also allowed the use of a tobramycin concentration of $0.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (about 26 times less).

The evaluation of the combinations involving the benzaldehydes with the antibiotics ciprofloxacin/tobramycin was also conducted through the calculation of the ΣCI (see Supplementary Data - Table S4). All interactions resulted in an additive effect in terms of biomass, metabolic activity and culturability reduction, except for the combination of syringaldehyde with tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$), which showed an antagonistic effect on the culturability.

3.6. Effect of the benzaldehydes on biofilm susceptibility to ciprofloxacin and tobramycin

The use of QSIs can increase the susceptibility of bacteria to antibiotics, making them more effective in eradicating bacterial infections. Bjarsholt et al. [69] emphasized the hypothesis that blocking QS not only increases sensitivity to antimicrobial treatments, but also makes bacteria more susceptible to elimination by the immune system. The authors demonstrated that bacterial biofilm in which QS is blocked, either by mutation or administration of QSI, are susceptible to treatment with tobramycin and H_2O_2 , and are readily phagocytosed by polymorphonuclear leukocytes, in contrast to bacteria with functioning QS

Fig. 13. - Effect of tobramycin, ciprofloxacin, benzaldehydes as well as their combinations (tobramycin + benzaldehyde (A) and ciprofloxacin + benzaldehyde (B)) against pre-established 24 h old *P. aeruginosa* biofilms, in terms of biofilm culturable cells [$\log(\text{CFU cm}^{-2})$]. Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with '*' are statistically different from tobramycin alone for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$), ns = non-significant. Bars with lowercase letters are statistically different from the control (biofilms without treatment and exposed to DMSO at 5 % or 2.5 %) for a confidence level greater than 95 % ($p < 0.05$, where a = **** and b = ns).

systems.

In this study, the susceptibility of 24 h old *P. aeruginosa* biofilms grown in the presence of the benzaldehydes to tobramycin ($1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) and ciprofloxacin ($1/32 \times \text{MIC}$) were investigated. For ciprofloxacin, a reduction in biofilm mass of ca. 66 % was obtained when the biofilm was grown in the presence of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Fig. 14A). The results showed that the application of benzaldehydes during biofilm formation allowed a 1.8-fold reduction of ciprofloxacin compared to its inhibitory concentration (at $5/4 \times \text{MIC}$) in previously untreated biofilms. In addition, this approach also enabled a lower dose of the ciprofloxacin, with a 40-fold reduction in its concentration. In the case of tobramycin, the application of benzaldehydes during biofilm formation only led to a slight reduction in biomass.

In terms of metabolic activity, tobramycin showed the greatest effect, achieving 32 %, 18 % and 20 % of reduction when administered with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde, respectively. For ciprofloxacin, the incubation of the benzaldehydes in the initial

phase resulted in reductions similar to the highest concentrations tested ($5/4 \times \text{MIC}$) (Fig. 14B).

With regard to the reduction of culturability, no significant differences were observed for the antibiotics used in this study when benzaldehydes were applied during biofilm formation (Fig. 14C). Therefore, all the benzaldehydes tend to increase biofilm susceptibility and improve antibiotic efficacy in reducing biofilm mass and metabolic activity. These results are comparable to the study by Hentzer et al. [70], who used the LIVE/DEAD assay to show that *P. aeruginosa* biofilms grown in the presence of a QSI (FC-30) were more susceptible to the effects of tobramycin.

In addition, Borges et al. [4], observed a significant reduction in biofilm mass (33 %) after pre-treatment of *P. aeruginosa* biofilms with furvina (at $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) followed by the addition of ciprofloxacin (at $40 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Similar results were obtained when the biofilms were pre-treated with selected benzaldehydes but only $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ciprofloxacin was used.

Fig. 14. - Susceptibility of 24-h-old *P. aeruginosa* biofilms formed in the presence of the benzaldehydes (at $500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to tobramycin (at $1/16 \times \text{MIC}$) and ciprofloxacin (at $1/32 \times \text{MIC}$) in terms of biomass removal (A), biofilm cells metabolic activity reduction (B) and biofilm culturable cells [$\log(\text{CFU cm}^{-2})$] (C). Mean values \pm standard deviations for at least three replicates are illustrated. Bars with '*' are statistically different from tobramycin and ciprofloxacin alone for a confidence level greater than 95% ($p < 0.05$), ne = no effect, ns = non-significant. Bars with lowercase letters are statistically different from the control (biofilms without treatment) for a confidence level greater than 95% ($p < 0,05$, where a = ns, b = ***, c = **, and d = ****).

4. Conclusions

The present study shows the inhibitory effect of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde on the *las* and *pqs* systems of *P. aeruginosa* and their ability to reduce pyocyanin production. The molecular docking studies corroborated the data obtained indicating the presence of strong interactions between the benzaldehydes and the key proteins of both QS systems. Their positions and higher docking scores, compared to the reference or known ligands, validate their potential as potent QSIs.

In addition, the combination of benzaldehydes with ciprofloxacin/tobramycin effectively prevented biofilm formation and destabilised pre-established biofilms by reducing biomass production, metabolic activity and culturable cells. In general, additive interactions between ciprofloxacin/tobramycin and benzaldehydes were observed in the control of biofilms. Furthermore, the use of benzaldehydes makes biofilms more susceptible to the action of ciprofloxacin/tobramycin and allows the administration of lower antibiotic doses. Therefore, benzaldehydes can be used in combination with less potent antibiotics to improve therapeutic efficacy in the treatment of biofilm-associated infections.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Miguel M. Leitão: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Tatiana F. Vieira:** Methodology. **Sérgio F. Sousa:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Fernanda Borges:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Manuel Simões:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Anabela Borges:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2024.106663>.

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